

Employees Job Satisfaction: Analyzing the satisfaction by length of Service and Employment status

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Abstract: The satisfaction of employees is extremely important to organization. The performance and efficiency of the organization totally relies on the satisfied employees. The satisfied employee tend to be creative and innovative and come up with the breakthroughs that make the company to grow and profitable.

This research investigates the satisfaction of employees in the organization. The research is focused on investigating the satisfaction of employees by their employment status and length of service. This research study is done in one of the service-oriented business organization with the agreement that her name will not be mentioned in the research paper. In this study, the employment status is hypothesized to the total staff satisfaction and length of service is hypothesized to the total staff satisfaction of employees.

Survey tool is used to let know the employer about employee's satisfaction level. The survey is a traditional method that involves employees' participation and employers conduct. They include questions in such a way that every aspect of an organization is touched and the feedback is returned in the form of an opinion given by each employee. These surveys help employers to understand employees thinking and their satisfaction levels, and that understanding paves the path for problem solving

Keywords: Organization, Human Resource, Employees satisfaction, Service Length

Introduction

The employee satisfaction in the organizations is paramount as this is what determines the success or failure of a company. When employees are satisfied and happy in terms of wages and benefits along with working environment in an organization, the customer is the first person to notice that. It completely depends on the employer to ensure they do not have their top talent drained away by the new competitor on the block. It has become essential for the employer to be aware and understand the signals that are given out by the employees. The management must put their efforts to readdress the due demands of the employees before it is too late and the employee makes the decision to quit. This understanding gives the employers an edge and a time to take corrective measures in order to prevent talent loss. It could be possible that the employee may not be happy with the environment or he may be suffering from a relationship issue with a colleague or a superior. These issues need to be handled before they get out of hand. It is a fact that employees work for money but emotional rewards go a long way at keeping the employer-employee relation strong and thus have a larger impact on employee satisfaction. The tracing and improving this satisfaction level has to be top priority for the HR department of an organization. [Marion, 1996]

The employees' satisfaction can be the key to a better motivated and loyal workforce that leads to better organizational output in the form of better products and services and results in overall improvement of an organization. The loyal and committed employees are the most influential factor to becoming an employer of choice. The organization and companies in this regard face significant challenges in developing energized and engaged workforces. However, the plenty of research has shown that increased employee commitment and trust in leadership can positively impact the company's bottom line. The veracity is that

potential of an organization can only be realized when the productivity level of all individuals and teams are fully aligned, committed and energized to successfully accomplish the goals of the organization (Bhatti & Qureshi, 2007)

The ambition of every company should be to improve the desire of employees to stay in the relationship which they have with the company. Whereas companies understand and manage employees' loyalty rather than retention, they can reap benefits on both sides of the balance sheet i.e., revenues and costs. On top of the revenue side of the balance sheet, loyal and committed employees are more likely to go "above and beyond" to meet customer needs and are highly motivated to work to the best of their ability. Both of these traits are crucial for continued customer commitment and ongoing revenue and growth for the company. Therefore, rather than focusing only on retention, organizations should proactively recognize the benefits of understanding, managing and improving employee loyalty. The majority of successful organizations are those that can adapt their organizational behavior to the realities of the current work environment where success is dependent upon innovation, creativity and flexibility. Furthermore, the dynamics of the work environment have to reflect a very diverse population comprised of individuals whose motivations, beliefs and value structures differ vastly from the past and from each other. Debatably, the most valuable, but also volatile, corporate asset is a stable workforce of competent, dedicated employees, since such an employee base gives companies a powerful advantage; depth of knowledge and organizational strength (Wright, Gardener & Allen, 2005)

The key steps to understanding and improving employee loyalty is by acknowledging the importance of the following factors in building loyalty and satisfaction:

- Broadly-defined responsibilities rather than narrowly-defined job functions
- Effective and regular performance evaluations, both formally and informally
- A corporate emphasis on employee learning, development and growth
- Wide-ranging employee participation in the organization as a whole

Normally, a combination of factors influences employees' decisions to stay at their current job. The contributing factors include satisfying work, a sense of job security, clear opportunities for advancement, a compelling corporate mission combined with the ability to contribute to the organization's success, and a feeling that their skills are being effectively used and challenged. The employees who enjoy their work identify themselves with their employer and perceive that the company is flexible regarding work and family issues also intend to stay with the organization (Loveman, 1998).

Now days, the employee loyalty needs to be earned, rather than assumed, and must be specific, rather than general - employees are looking at their employment as a means of achieving personal goals rather than simply being the "good corporate soldier" of the past. This signifies that companies need to express and act on a commitment to develop employees' career objectives by introducing initiatives that make employees believe that their current job is the best path to achieving their career goals(Loveman, 1998).

Literature Review

There has been enough research done on the employees' satisfaction in the organization in various ways. The research study has found that by understanding the concerns of employees, companies could be better able to implement policies and procedures that can create strong commitment and loyalty of

employees towards the organization. Under the concept of employees' satisfaction, the major concerns are taken into account by asking the following questions;

1. How to increase the sense of commitment and loyalty of the employees?
2. What kind of benefits and emoluments can increase the commitment and satisfaction?
3. How to gain the trust of employees?

The previous research studies have shown that employees' satisfaction has a direct relationship to the business revenue and customer loyalty. Satisfied employees perform better at their job and unsatisfied employees can have a negative effect on their co-workers and their customers. The most of the experts who have done their research in this area of organization believe that one of the best ways to maintain employee's satisfaction is to make worker feel like a part of family or team. The holding office events such as parties, group outings can help build close bonds among workers. The increase in salary and bonuses can affect employee's satisfaction, but that only cannot solve all moral issues of employees. When companies with wide spread problems for workers could not improve their overall environment then wages benefits would not be much effective in the overall satisfaction of employees (Locke, 1976)

During 2005, the Insight link National Employee Satisfaction study shows that only 21% of U.S. employees feel fully committed to their employers and only 12% agree that their employers are fully committed to them. However, the degree of commitment between employees and employers is directly linked to the level of job satisfaction expressed by employees. The employees who are extremely satisfied with their jobs, 94% also feel extremely or very committed to their employers. In compare to this the employees who are not very satisfied where

only 13% feel that level of commitment. Employees' satisfaction is a measure of how happy workers are with their job and working environment (Insightlink, 2004).

The happy worker will likely be more productive and stay loyal to the company. There are many factors in improving or maintaining high employee satisfaction. The major factors have shown in the following

framework, which may impact the total staff satisfaction of the employees in the organization. This research paper has taken only two factors for the study i.e employment status and length of service. The following figure depicts the framework of factors of Employees job satisfaction. These are known as important indicators for the employees' satisfaction in the organization.

According to the above framework, the Employment status is hypothesized to the total staff satisfaction of employees in the organization and the Length of service is hypothesized to the total staff satisfaction of employees in the organization.

Methodology

The sample of population is related to the employees of the organization. It consists of 500 sample of respondent. The survey is conducted from different 8 cities of the branches of same organization. The questionnaire instrument is used in the survey for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of 20 items and each item is directed to ask different questions related to the level of satisfaction with their jobs, working environment, benefits and employee and employer relations in the organization. The respondents have been divided into two categories i.e permanent and casual employees.

The scale is constructed to measure the total staff satisfaction of employees according to

the employment status of the employees' satisfaction with respect to pays and benefits, comfortable with the working environment that creates loyalty and commitment to the organization. The respondents were asked to rate their satisfaction with the pays and benefits and working environment. Five point Likert scale is used to ask the response from respondent. The level of agreement is rated on the following scale; Agreement: (1= not at all, 2= slight extent, 3 = moderate extent 4 = great extent, 5 = very great extent) .

The Cronbach's alpha for the 10 item scale is 0.0873

The data is consisting of two groups of employees' i.e permanent employee and casual employee .The purpose of this data analysis is to measure the employee's satisfaction on the basis of employment status and service length.

- Independent Sample T-test is selected for analyzing the level of satisfaction between the two groups of employees, i.e permanent employee and casual employees.
- Similarly, for measuring the direction of relationship between the two variables i.e

service length of the employee and total staff satisfaction, Pearson r test is selected.

Research Findings

Descriptive statistics is used to describe the basic features of sample data in study. These statistics provides simple summaries about the sample measures. These are used to present quantities descriptions in manageable form.

Descriptions of sample population

<i>EmployeesTypes</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i> %
Permanent employees	311	62.2
Casual employees	177	35.4
Missing cases	12	2.4
Total	500	100%

Table-1

The above table-1 shows that there are 311 numbers of permanent employees and 177 casual employees.

Employees' satisfaction according to the employment status

The data is consisting of two groups of the same population i.e permanent employees and casual employees.

	Employment status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Total Staff Satisfaction Scale	Permanent	287	33.93	7.147
	Casual	161	34.20	7.099

Table-2

The table-2 shows total staff satisfaction mean 33.93 for permanent employees with standard deviation 7.147 and 34.20 mean for casual employees with standard deviation 7.099.The following graph has been derived from the above table. The graph demonstrates the number of permanent and causal employees in the organization.

Graph-2

The graph-2 also presents the number of employees groups and their mean score levels. Looking at the means score of two groups in table-2 as well as in graph-2, it is found that there is no significance difference between the means score of two groups. Therefore we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no difference in the satisfaction level of these two groups.

Employment Status		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means		
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Total Staff Satisfaction Scale	Equal variances assumed	.040	.842	-.391	446	.696

Table-3

The result in the table-3 shows that the sig value of Levene's Test for equality of variance 0.842, which is larger than the value of significance level 0.05, it means that there is no difference between two groups. As there is no difference in the satisfaction level between these two groups, therefore, it is concluded that employment status does not affect the total staff satisfaction of the employees in the organization.

Employees' satisfaction by service length groups

In order to analyze the satisfaction level of each group, the one way analysis of variance is selected. Analysis of variance compares the variance between the groups with the variability within each of groups. The sample population is consisting of three groups by their length of service.. These groups are mentioned in the following table.

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
By service length			
1<= 2	162	35.73	6.477
3 - 5	121	33.28	6.637
6+	126	33.33	7.722
Total	409	34.27	7.014

Table-4

The table-4 shows number of cases N= 409 of sample size 500. In the table, there are three groups by the length of service, the first group is includes 162 employees with the mean score 35.73, the second group includes 121 employees with the mean score 33.28 and third groups includes 126 employees with the mean score 33.33.

Graph-3

Looking at the mean score of all three groups in the table-6 and graph-2, it is found that there is no any significance difference in the level of satisfaction between these service groups. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that service length does not have any impact on the total staff satisfaction of the employees in the organization.

Conclusion

The study survey is conducted to analyze the satisfaction level amongst the employees of service –oriented organization. The data is collected from 500 employees, serving into different branches of organization. The sample population consisted to two groups of employee; one is permanent employees and other is casual employees. The data statistic shows that, there are 311 permanent employees and 177 casual employees in the sample population.

The research study on Employees job satisfaction by length of Service and Employment status has concluded that employees have same level of job satisfaction amongst the both groups of employee’s i.e permanent and casual employees by status, therefore, employee’s status does not have any impact on the job satisfaction of the employees of the organization. Similarly, employee’s job satisfaction by service length groups have been also analyzed. It is concluded from the

result that service length does not have any impact on the job satisfaction of the employees in the organization.

In the context of employees job satisfaction, different Human Resource theories has claimed that there are many other factors i.e perks and wages, work environment, job security and organizational standards are very much countable in the job satisfaction of the employees.

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